

Evidences of Adenine-Thymine Interactions at Gold Electrodes Interfaces as provided by in situ Infrared Spectroscopy

Manuela Rueda^{(a)*}, Francisco Prieto^(a), Julia Álvarez^(a), Antonio Rodes^(b)

^(a)*Department of Physical Chemistry. University of Seville. C/ Profesor García González nº 2, 41012 Seville (Spain). tfn. +34954556733, e-mail: marueda@us.es*

^(b)*Department of Physical Chemistry and Institute of Electrochemistry. University of Alicante. Ap. 99, E-03080, Alicante (Spain)*

Abstract

The co-adsorption of complementary DNA bases adenine and thymine on gold thin-film electrodes from 0.1M HClO₄ solutions in H₂O and D₂O is studied by surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy in the attenuated total reflection mode (ATR-SEIRAS). The comparison of the spectra in the range 1750-1550 cm⁻¹ for co-adsorbed adenine and thymine at controlled potentials to those of the individual adsorbed bases show the enhancement of the signals associated to the vibration modes of adenine and the inhibition of those of thymine. The results can be explained by invoking the rearrangement of both molecules on the electrode surface in order to facilitate the Watson-Crick (W-C) and/or Hoogsteen (HG) interactions between the bases. The co-adsorption seems to be a cooperative process in which a low surface concentration of each base can induce the rearrangement of the complementary base molecules on the surface.

Keywords

Adenine; thymine; adsorption; gold electrodes; ATR-SEIRAS

1. Introduction

Adenine and thymine are complementary nucleic acid bases that provide replication and transcription of the genetic codes in living cells by double H-bonding either in the Watson-Crick (W-C) [1] or the Hoogsteen (HG) [2] configurations (Fig. 1a). The interactions between DNA bases play decisive roles also in enzymatic and protein organization processes.

The study of the interactions of these bases at the organized electrode interfaces can be interesting for understanding their activities in biological media and for biotechnology and nanotechnology applications.

In-situ infrared spectroscopy can provide evidences about the disposition of the molecules on the surface, the coordination sites with the metal and the intermolecular interactions. Particularly, surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy in the Kretschmann attenuated total reflection (ATR-SEIRAS) mode allows high sensitivity studies of adsorbed molecules with little interference from the solution [3].

We have studied adenine adsorption on gold electrodes in previous papers where an adsorption model was proposed consisting of slightly tilted adenine molecules coordinated to the metal by the N atoms of the amino group and by the N₇ atom [4-7]. On the other hand, for thymine adsorption on gold electrodes several adsorption states have been described depending on the applied potential [8-10]: a chemisorbed phase, at high potentials, in which the molecules coordinate to the metal with both oxygen atoms and a deprotonated N₃ atom in a vertically organisation, stabilized by π -stacking interactions and a condensed but weakly adsorbed adlayer stabilised by H-bonds, at lower potentials. Interestingly, the same atoms of adenine and thymine involved in the chemical interactions with the metal would also be participating in the W-C and HG interactions: N₁₀H and N₁ (W-C interaction) or N₇ (HG interaction) of adenine and the oxygen on C₄ and N₃H of thymine.

In this paper the advantages of ATR-SEIRAS are explored in order to decide about the interactions of co-adsorbed adenine and thymine molecules on gold thin-film electrodes in acid media as compared to the separated adsorption of the two bases. Experiments were carried out both in water and deuterium oxide solutions and the spectra for deuterated and non-deuterated adsorbed species analysed.

2. - Experimental

Working solutions were 0.1M HClO₄ (Merck Suprapur) in Purelab ultra water or in D₂O (Sigma Aldrich 99.96%). Adenine and thymine (Sigma Aldrich) were used as received. Adenine and thymine solutions with concentrations ranging from 1x 10⁻⁵ to 1x 10⁻³ M were prepared by spiking 1x 10⁻² M stock solutions made in the same supporting electrolyte. Solutions were deaerated by bubbling argon.

The voltammetry experiments were performed with Au(111) single crystal electrodes prepared and cleaned as indicated in [6]. In the ATR-SEIRAS experiments, gold thin-film electrodes (ca 25nm thick) were used, prepared by argon sputtering on one of the sides of a silicon prism bevelled at 60° (Pastec, Japan). Deposition rate was 0.01 nm s⁻¹. A gold foil and a reversible hydrogen electrode were used as counter and reference electrodes, respectively. All potentials are referred to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE).

Infrared experiments were performed in the Kretschmann configuration using a Nicolet 6700 spectrometer, equipped with a narrow-band MCT-A detector. Spectral resolution was 4 cm⁻¹. 100 interferograms were accumulated in the single-beam experiments at each potential. Background spectra were registered under the same conditions either in the base-free supporting electrolyte or before de addition of the second base. The spectra are presented as the ratio $-\log(R_2/R_1)$, where R₂ and R₁ are the reflectance values corresponding to the sample and reference single-beam spectra, respectively. A CHI Instrument potentiostat was used for potential control.

The gold electrode surfaces were treated in order to get the lifting of the reconstruction of the (111) domains in the supporting electrolyte by slowly scanning the potential from -0.1 V to 0.7 V, at which they are kept for a few minutes. The two bases were added at electrode potentials at which both can chemically adsorb.

3.- Results

3.1.- Voltammetry results

Typical voltammograms obtained in thymine solutions (Fig.1b) show a peak at 0.440 V corresponding to chemical desorption, followed by characteristic transition of phase couple of peaks, which delimit the potential region corresponding to a condensed layer of physically adsorbed thymine [8]. The voltammograms in adenine solutions show that this base remains chemically adsorbed in a wider potential range, the desorption peak appearing around 0.060V. Addition of adenine to chemically adsorbed thymine induces the shift of thymine desorption peak to lower potentials and the disappearance of the transition of phase signals

3.2.- ATR-SEIRAS spectra in deuterium oxide

Some results are given in Figs 2a and 2b. The more significant signals in the infrared spectra of adenine and thymine appear in the region 1750-1450 cm^{-1} . Chemically adsorbed deuterated adenine shows a surface active signal around 1650 cm^{-1} , assigned to a skeletal stretching mode within the pyrimidine ring [11] while the spectrum of chemically adsorbed deuterated thymine provides three signals at 1649, 1581 and 1567 cm^{-1} related to the stretching modes of the $\text{C}_2=\text{O}$, $\text{C}_4=\text{O}$ and $\text{C}_5=\text{C}_6$ double-bonds [12,13]. At lower potentials, at which thymine is physically adsorbed the double-bond stretching modes of this molecule are not surface active because of the flat orientation of the molecular plane on the electrode [8-10].

Two set of experiments have been performed in order to compare the spectra of co-adsorbed deuterated bases to those of the individual adsorbed bases, each experiment starting with a different base. The effects of adding adenine to adsorbed thymine are illustrated in parts i) while the results of thymine addition to adsorbed adenine are shown in part ii). At a high potential at which both bases get chemically adsorbed, the strong signal related to the adenine ring-stretching mode shifts towards somewhat higher wavenumbers (1654 cm^{-1}) and its intensity is significantly enhanced with respect to the spectrum for adsorbed adenine in the absence of thymine. On the other hand, the two thymine signals at lower wavenumbers due to the $\text{C}_4=\text{O}$ and the $\text{C}_5=\text{C}_6$ bonds almost disappear when adding adenine. It is not evident from a simple inspection to decide about the thymine signal at higher wavenumbers because the overlapping with the adenine signal. However, deconvolution of the peak at 1654 cm^{-1} provides only one band with the same half- width than obtained in the case of adsorbed adenine alone but with higher intensity. These effects can be better observed in the spectra of co-adsorbed bases when calculated using as references the single beam spectra of the individual bases: The displacement/reorientation of adsorbed thymine induced by adenine co-adsorption gives rise to negative signals in the spectra (parts i) while the enhancement of the mode of adenine when co-adsorbed is evident in the positive signals in part ii). The enhancement of the adenine signal when adding thymine is still visible (although less intense) at lower potentials at which only adenine is chemically adsorbed but thymine can form physically condensed layer.

3.3.- ATR-SEIRAS spectra in water

The results in water solutions are illustrated in Fig. 2c. It can be observed that the spectra of chemically adsorbed adenine yield in the absence of thymine a wide and strong signal at 1677 cm^{-1} which after deconvolution shows to be the combination of two bands at 1679 and 1663 cm^{-1} , respectively assigned to the amine group and to the ring vibrations [6,7,11]. Chemically adsorbed thymine presents now two strong groups of signals at 1658 and 1600 cm^{-1} , assigned to the two carbonyl double-bond vibration modes coupled to the neighbour carbon-carbon double bond [12-13]. Addition of adenine to chemically adsorbed thymine (part i) induces the decrease of the two thymine signals and the development of a wide adenine signal, which is more intense than that for adsorbed adenine in the absence of thymine. The enhancement of the adsorbed adenine signals are also detected in the case of addition of thymine to chemically adsorbed adenine (part ii). Deconvolution of the main adenine signal in the spectra of the co-adsorbed bases shows that, in fact, the enhancement of the amino group signal (at ca. 1679 cm^{-1}) is higher than that of the ring-stretching mode (ca. 1663 cm^{-1}).

Similar results to those reported in Figures 2 for working solutions with an adenine concentration lower than that of thymine are obtained irrespectively of the relative adenine and thymine concentrations in the range between 0.001 and 1 mM .

4.- Discussion and Conclusions

Since the atoms involved in the W-C and HG interactions are also involved in the vibration modes that provide the bands described above, we consider the possibility that the changes observed upon co-adsorption are related to the formation of the H-bonds in the corresponding adsorbed adenine-thymine pairs. The two bases can also interact by H-bonds with themselves and with the solvent, so the determination of the effects of H-bonds in the vibrational spectra relies on the comparison of the experimental or calculated spectra of isolated molecules with the spectra of molecules in liquid or solid phases [13,14]. Thus, it has been proposed [14] that thymine forms hydrogen bonds $\text{C}_2=\text{O}_8\cdots\text{HN}_1$ and $\text{C}_2=\text{O}_8\cdots\text{HN}_3$ in the polycrystalline state while in the aqueous phase the $\text{O}_8\cdots\text{HO}$ and $\text{O}\cdots\text{HN}_1$ predominate. For the spectra of isolated W-C adenine-thymine pair the calculations predict four delocalized normal modes, which are red-shifted with respect to the C=O stretching modes of isolated thymine but blue shifted with respect to characteristic adenine signals in the $1750\text{-}1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region [15]. However, our transmission spectra of 10mM thymine + 10mM adenine in D_2O and in H_2O solutions (not shown) reveal that the signals of thymine and adenine in this region do not change significantly when compared to those of the corresponding 10mM solutions of each base alone. Thus, it seems that in aqueous solutions the distinction of H-bonds between complementary base pairs and those between each of the bases and water is practically impossible.

Nevertheless, the interactions between the two bases when adsorbed on the electrode can still be inferred from our ATR-SEIRAS results as they seem to imply changes in the organisation of the two bases on the electrode. The adsorption model proposed for the adsorption of adenine assumed bonding through the N_{10} and N_7 atoms [6, 7] and implies the sp^3 hybridization of N_{10} . However, this configuration is not suitable for the W-C or HG interactions, so the adsorbed adenine molecule should turn on the surface in order to facilitate the double H-bonds with co-adsorbed thymine using the N_3 and N_9

atoms to interact with the metal. This implies a higher tilt angle that would give rise to an enhancement of the intensity of the ring stretching mode since the latter involves the pyrimidine ring and the C₆-N₁₀ bond [11]. The enhancement should be even higher for the scissoring mode of the amino group, as experimentally observed. On the other hand, thymine molecule can use the N₃ and the oxygen atoms to interact with adsorbed adenine instead of the metal [8-10] and get adsorbed by π -interactions with the electrode adopting a more flat orientation on the surface.

The fact that very small amounts of each base (at the sub-monolayer level) induce significant changes in the spectra of the complementary base, even when adsorbed from solutions with a higher concentration of the complementary base suggests that the co-adsorption of adenine and thymine is a cooperative event in which interaction mechanisms may include also stacking and dipole-dipole interactions.

It can then be concluded that adenine molecule changes the sites of interaction with the electrode from the N₁₀ and N₇ atoms to the N₃ and N₉ atoms adopting a more upright orientation on the electrode in the presence of co-adsorbed thymine, thus facilitating the H-bonds with the complementary base. On the contrary, thymine reorients toward a flat disposition that allows the two H-bonds of the W-C or HG types with adsorbed adenine and the simultaneous π -interaction of the ring with the metal. Organised structures involving also other kinds of interactions are suggested to be formed in a cooperative process.

Acknowledgements

Financial support from Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia (Spain) (Projects CTQ2010-19823 and CTQ2009-13142 and a FPU-grant to JA), Junta de Andalucía (Grupo FQM202) and Generalitat Valenciana (ACOMP/2011/200) are greatly acknowledged.

References

- 1 J.D. Watson, F.H.C. Crick, *Nature* 171 (1953) 737.
- 2 K. Hoogsteen, *Acta Crystallogr.* 12 (1959) 822.
- 3 M. Osawa in C. Alkire, D. Kolb, J.Lipkowski, P.N. Ross (Eds.), *Diffraction and Spectroscopic Methods in Electrochemistry*, Wiley-VCH: Weinheim 2006; Vol.9 pp 269-314.
- 4 C. Prado, F. Prieto, M. Rueda, J. Feliu, A. Aldaz, *Electrochim. Acta* 52 (2007) 3168.
- 5 F. Prieto, M. Rueda, C. Prado, J. Feliu, A. Aldaz, *Electrochim. Acta* 55 (2010) 301.
- 6 A. Rodes, M. Rueda, F. Prieto, C. Prado, J.M. Feliu, A. Aldaz, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 113 (2009) 18784.
- 7 M. Rueda, F. Prieto, A. Rodes and J.M. Delgado, *Electrochim. Acta*, 82 (2012) 534.

- 8 B. Roelfs, E. Bunge, C. Schröter, T. Solomun, H. Meyer, R.J. Nichols, H. Baumgärtel, *J.Phys.Chem. B* 101 (1997) 754.
- 9 W. Haiss, B. Roelfs, S.N. Port, E. Bunge, H. Baumgärtel, R.J. Nichols, *J.Electroanal.Chem.* 454 (1998) 107.
- 10 W-H. Li, W. Haiss, S. Floate, R.J. Nichols, *Langmuir* 15 (1999) 4875.
- 11 B. Giese, D. McNaughton, *J.Phys.Chem. B* 106 (2002) 101 ???
- 12 J.S. Singh, *J.Mol.Struct.* 876 (2008) 127
- 13 A. Aamouche, M. Ghomi, C. Coulombeau, L. Grajcar, M.H. Baron, H. Jobic, G. Berthier, *J.Phys.Chem. A* 101 (1997) 1808
- 14 G.N. Ten, T.G. Burova, V.I. Baranov, *J. Appl. Spectroscopy* 72(1) (2005) 104
- 15 G.N. Ten, V.V. Nechaev, A.N. Pankratov, V.I. Baranov, *J.Struct. Chem.* 51(3) (2010) 453

Figure Captions

Figure Captions

Fig.1 a): Adenine and thymine molecules and W-C and HG interactions. b): Voltammograms obtained in (T) 1mM thymine (- - -), (A) 0.01 mM adenine (-.-.-) and (T+A) 1mM thymine+0.01 mM adenine (____) 0.1 M HClO₄ solutions. $v = 0.1$ V/s.

Fig. 2 ATR-SEIRAS spectra collected at indicated potentials after addition of adenine (till 0.01mM) to 1mM thymine solution (____, i) or after addition of thymine (till 1mM) to 0.01 mM adenine solution (____, ii). Test electrolyte: 0.1 M HClO₄ in D₂O (Figures 2a and 2b) and in H₂O (Figure 2c). Each spectrum is referred to that collected in the supporting electrolyte at the same potential in the absence of the bases except the bold-dashed lines, which are referred to the corresponding spectrum collected in solutions containing only thymine (____, i)) or only adenine (____, ii)). The spectra collected at the same potentials in the individual base solutions, 1mM thymine (-.-.-) or 0.01 mM adenine (-.-.-) are also given.

Highlights

- Addition of adenine to a solution of thymine extends the potential range at which both molecules can be co-adsorbed on gold electrodes, as revealed by the voltammograms of Au(111) electrodes.
- ATR-SEIRAS spectra of adsorbed adenine and thymine on gold electrodes show strong signals in the range 1750-1550 cm^{-1} , due to vibration modes involving the amino group and the pyrimidine ring of adenine molecule and the carbonyl and double C=C bonds of the thymine molecule.
- The spectra of co-adsorbed bases when compared to those of the individual bases show the enhancement of the signals of adenine molecule and the decrease of those of thymine molecule.
- It is proposed that both molecules reorient on the electrode surface upon co-adsorption in order to facilitate the two H-bonds of the W-C or HG interactions: adenine molecule changes the site of interaction with the electrode from the N₁₀ and N₇ atoms to the N₃ and N₉ atoms adopting a more upright orientation on the electrode, while thymine molecule adopt a flat disposition when both molecules are co-adsorbed.
- The co-adsorption seems to be a cooperative process involving also other kind of interactions, as only a few molecules of each base can induce the reorganisation of a higher number of adsorbed molecules of the complementary base on the surface.

a)

b)

Figure 1

1700 1600 1500

Wavenumber / cm⁻¹

Figure 2a

1700 1600 1500

Wavenumber / cm⁻¹

Figure 2b

1700 1600 1500

Wavenumber / cm⁻¹

Figure 2c